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Solid Oxide Cells Development in China

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Abstract

Both Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) and Solid oxide electrolysis cell (SOEC) develop very quickly in the world recently. This work details the growth and evolution of SOFC technology from fundamental science to engineering in China. Supported by the Chinese National 973 Program of MOST (Ministry of Science and Technology of China) from 2011 to 2016, fundamental research was carried out to clear the scientific issues in SOFC area, including the construction of the cell structure and its electrochemical behavior, the coupled mechanisms of multi-physics and multi-scale in SOFC, as well as the energy management and analysis of overall system. Currently, the degradation mechanism of SOFC and durability enhancement, supported by National Key R&D Program of China from 2019 to 2023, is engaging in China. Meanwhile, the SOFC industry chain *from powder to power* has been constructed to solve the engineering issues, including materials preparation, cell manufacture, stack assembly and system integration. The first SOFC production line with the scale of 200,000 cells per year has been put into service in Xuzhou City, Jiangsu Province since August, 2019. Based on the scale-up of the cells and stacks, a coal-based fuel cell integrated demonstration system has been designed and built in Shanxi Province. Another highlighted national project in China is the *Coal Gasification Power System with Near Zero CO₂ Emission*, which is also supported by National Key R&D Program of China from 2017 to 2021. All these works will lay a foundation for practical application of SOFC technology in China, providing contributions to the future clean and high efficiency power plants using coal and other fuels. Meanwhile, SOEC related research has also lasted for years in China, which is mainly supported by local governments. From 2019, a SOEC demonstration project has been implemented by Tsinghua Team together with CHN ENERGY Investment Group Co. LTD, supported by Beijing Science and Technology Commission.

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1. Introduction

China's coal based natural resources determine the energy consumption structure dominated by coal in the short term. At present, thermal power accounts for more than 60% of total power generation in China, while the world average is about 38% [1]. Therefore, carbon emissions and pollution from coal utilization have attracted the greatest attention of all institutions, as the Chinese government has promised to achieve carbon neutrality by 2060 [2]. On the one hand, China has carried out a thorough technical transformation of coal-fired power plants, realizing the clean upgrading of the whole process [3,4]. On the other hand, renewable energy and hydrogen related technologies have also been strongly supported and demonstrated in recent years [1].

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) have attracted more and more attention due to their high electrical efficiency and fuel flexibility. The basic research on SOFC in Chinese academic institutions began around 2000, mainly supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC). Since 2011, the Ministry of science and technology of China (MOST) has supported comprehensive fundamental research, technology development and engineering demonstration of SOFCs through National Program on Key Basic Research Project (973 Program), National High-tech R&D Program of China (863 Program) and on-going National Key R&D Program of China. Besides, with the rapid development of renewable power in recent years, high temperature solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOECs) and reversible solid oxide cells (RSOCs) have also attracted the interest of large enterprises and local governments in China.

2. Fundamental Research

From 2012 to 2016, with the support of the 973 Program of MOST, more than ten research institutes, universities and companies cooperated to carry out comprehensive fundamental research, mainly to solve the scientific problems and practical applications of high-efficiency, reliable and low-cost SOFCs using carbon-based fuels, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Project *Fundamental Research on Carbon-Based Fuel SOFC Systems* (2012-2016) supported by CHN 973 Program

3. Technology Research and Development

Since 2018, with the support of the National Key R&D Program of China, two projects for single cell and stack lifetime extension have been launched. By studying the attenuation mechanism of single cells and key components in the stack, the degradation rate of short stack ($W_e=500$ W) will be reduced to less than 0.5%/1000 hrs. The expected lifetime of the mass-produced kilowatt stack will be more than 10,000 hours.

Figure 2. Project *Degradation Mechanism and Long Life Strategy of High Efficiency SOFCs* (2018-2023) supported by National Key R&D Program of China

Another highlighted project is the research on clean and efficient utilization of coal based on advanced coal gasification and purification technologies, high temperature fuel cells (MCFC and SOFC), and CO₂ capture and utilization, which is also supported by the National Key R&D Program of China. Based on this project, the first MW_{th} integrated coal gasification and fuel cell (IGFC) demonstration system with near zero CO₂ emission will be built, with electrical efficiency more than 50% and CO₂ capture rate more than 90%.

Figure 3. Project *Coal Gasification Power System with Near Zero CO₂ Emission* (2017-2021) supported by National Key R&D Program of China

Regarded as the best choice for the utilization of excess renewable power, SOEC-related technology research and development have also been carried out with the support of local governments in China in recent years. From 2019, a demonstration project of 1 kW SOEC system has been implemented by Tsinghua Team together with CHN ENERGY Investment Group Co.,Ltd., which is supported by Beijing Science and Technology Commission. Under the background of current energy structure reform, SOEC technology can be combined with redundant thermal power or renewable power generation to produce H₂ and other sustainable fuels, which is an indispensable link in the future new energy network.

4. Industrial Development and Demonstration

The application prospect of SOFCs in the fields of distributed power generation and power system of vehicles has attracted the attention of some local governments and enterprises, which has accelerated the industrialization of SOFCs in China. The first SOFC mass production line with the scale of 200,000 single cells per year constructed by Xuzhou Huaqing Jingkun Energy Co.,Ltd. has been put into service since August, 2019. Another company, Chaozhou Three Circle Co.,Ltd., also has the mass production capacity of SOFC electrolyte, single cells and stacks. At the system level, a coal-based fuel cell integrated demonstration system has been designed and built in Shanxi Province in 2018. The maximum output power of the system is 15 kW, and the longest continuous operation time is nearly 1000 hours when using coal derived gas fuel.

Figure 4. Coal-based SOFC demonstration system in Jincheng, Shanxi province, China.

Besides, Weichai Power Co., Ltd. and Ceres Power jointly developed a stack with 30 kW output power, which will further be applied in commercial vehicles. At present, Weichai and Ceres plan to develop 10 bus systems and complete the verification in 2020.

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